

Semi-empirical AM1 investigations of geometric and electronic effects in benzyne mechanism

Kishor Arora^{a*} and D. Kumar^b

^aGovernment Autonomous K. R. G. College, Gwalior-474 002, India

^bGovernment Autonomous Science College, Gwalior-474 009, India

E-mail : kishorarora@rediffmail.com docdkumar@yahoo.com

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Semi-empirical quantum chemical AM1 methodology has been employed to find out various geometric and electronic effects in benzyne mechanism reaction. Reasonable trends in activation barriers with different substituents are obtained. The computed results have been interpreted on the basis of the geometric features.

We report here the studies of geometric and electronic factors for benzyne mechanism which includes 1,2-elimination of haloarenes followed by nucleophilic addition. This mechanism involves deprotonation by a strong base followed by departure of halide anion.

The AM1 Hamiltonian¹ in the MOPAC package² was used to calculate the bond lengths, bond angles, heat of formations, core-core repulsion energies, ionization potential etc. Structures of molecules were drawn on the PCMODEL package of Serena software³ and then optimized which was used as input for MOPAC². These calculations were done for the reactions given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Reactions which proceeds via benzyne mechanism for which AM1 computations are done.

Results and Discussion

The computed heat of formations for various starting haloarenes/substituted haloarenes, intermediate benzyne formed and the product aminoarenes on the basis of AM1 calculations are shown in Table 1. The AM1 computed

energy profiles (Fig. 2) for these benzyne mechanism reactions are plotted on the basis of heat of formation data obtained for these species which revealed that these mechanisms correspond to one-step process which proceeds via formation of benzyne intermediate in each case. These reactions are shown in Fig. 1. The computed bond distances for various species involved in these reactions under study are given in Table 2. Trends for core-core repulsion, electronic energy, total energy and ionization potentials for the various species are given in Table 3. Core-core repulsion first decreases for various benzyne intermediates as compared to the starting haloarenes/substituted halo arenes and these

Table 1. AM1 computed heat of formation (kcal mol⁻¹) of the reactant haloarenes/substituted haloarenes, intermediate benzynes and the product aminoarenes

Arenes/ substituted arenes	ΔH_f (reactant)	Intermediate benzyne	ΔH_f (benzyne)	Product formed	ΔH_f (Product)
1	26.75191	2	140.47048	3	20.49321
4	8.19266	5	134.21851	6	13.28397

values increase for the product amino arenes while electronic energy and total energy increase in the case of benzyne intermediates as compared to starting haloarenes and then decrease for various aminoarenes formed. Trends in the ionization potentials for these species reveal that the value of ionization potential first increases in the case of various benzynes intermediates and then decreases during the formation of product amino arenes. It is because of the fact that benzynes are less stable species as compared to

Table 2. AM1 computed carbon-carbon bond lengths (Å) for reactions under study

Compound 1		Compound 2		Compound 3	
Atom number	Bond length	Atom number	Bond length	Atom number	Bond length
1-2	1.39449	1-2	1.41837	1-2	1.41483
2-3	1.39459	2-3	1.41183	2-3	1.39007
3-4	1.39459	3-4	1.41838	3-4	1.39404
4-5	1.39449	4-5	1.37382	4-5	1.39404
5-6	1.30810	5-6	1.25872	5-6	1.39008
Compound 4		Compound 5		Compound 6	
Atom number	Bond length	Atom number	Bond length	Atom number	Bond length
1-2	1.39872	1-2	1.42312	1-2	1.39691
2-3	1.39400	2-3	1.41069	2-3	1.39429
3-4	1.39416	3-4	1.41873	3-4	1.38861
4-5	1.39833	4-5	1.37384	4-5	1.41556
5-6	1.39793	5-6	1.25733	5-6	1.41355

Fig. 2. AM1 computed energy profiles for the reaction proceeding via benzyne mechanism.

the reactant haloarenes and product aminoarenes which in turn are comparatively more stable species. The twist angles in the intermediate benzyne are also comparable. AM1 results obtained for the species involved in the reactions under study confirm the fact that these reactions proceed via benzyne formation.

Table 3. AM1 computed core-core repulsion, electronic energy, total energy and IPs to the reactant haloarenes/substituted haloarenes, intermediate benzyne and the products

Compd. no.	Core-core repulsion (eV)	Electronic energy (eV)	Total energy (eV)	Ionization potential
1	3099.13930	-4289.08853	-1189.94923	9.60102
2	2121.27804	-2939.16658	-817.88854	9.90843
3	3287.4360	-4358.80235	-1071.36616	8.52234
4	3975.22052	-5545.75612	-1570.53560	9.68225
5	2811.63598	-3989.5961	-1177.95963	9.78056
6	4122.19864	-5553.67715	-1431.47851	8.73682

Conclusion : Analysis of AM1 computed geometries of the species involved in the reaction under study reveals a near optimal orthogonal geometry for benzyne intermediates. Increase in energies and heat of formation for benzyne intermediate is observed during the formation of intermediates which is indicative of increase in bond order in carbon-carbon bond which is a common factor in all the intermediates. This is shown in the energy profiles also. Thus, AM1 method proves to be quite reasonable giving good results for the case under study.

References

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